

A spore suspension was sprayed onto the border row of each plot to provide a source of inoculum. Disease was assessed at the milk stage and 1 wk before harvest. Number of infected panicles, degree of disease severity, and yield were recorded from selected areas in each experimental plot 1 × 2 m².

We found a close relationship between disease incidence and disease severity ($r^2 = 0.93$), and between disease severity and yield ($r^2 = 0.63$). Yield loss was calculated as

$$\frac{(\text{Yield of disease-free plot} - \text{yield of infected plot})}{\text{Yield of disease-free plot}} \times 100$$

When disease severity is high, grain loss increases. We obtained a significant regression function of percent yield loss on disease severity ($y = 4.287 \times -0.146$, $R^2 = 0.623$) (see figure). □

A new weed host for rice yellow dwarf (RYD) pathogen

A. V. Reddy and R. Jeyarajan, Plant Pathology Department, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We screened 19 weed species for susceptibility to RYD by inoculating 20 plants/species with 5 RYD-viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* per plant for 24 h.

Only *Echinochloa colona* developed symptoms similar to those caused by the RYD agent on rice. Symptoms appeared 43 d after inoculation (DAI) at the base of some tillers in 40% of the plants. RYD symptoms appeared 28.5 DAI in control rice variety TN1. When shoots of infected weed plants were cut at ground level, all the new growth showed RYD symptoms.

Weed species that did not show symptoms were *Cyperus rotundus*, *C. difformis*, *C. iria*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Ammannia baccifera*, *Brachiaria mutica*, *Chenopodium album*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Digitaria setigera*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *E. glabrescens*, *Eleusine indica*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Panicum capillare*, and *Portulaca oleracea*.

To test whether *E. colona* can transmit RYD to rice, one infected *E. colona* plant was used as an inoculum source for 50 *N. virescens*. Rice plants were inoculated with five viruliferous leafhoppers each. The RYD agent was

transmitted to 60% of the rice plants. Incubation period in rice was 30.8 d. Tiller numbers increased 224% and height of infected rice plants was 20 cm less than that of healthy rice plants. □

Status of brown spot (BS) and narrow brown leaf spot (NBLs) in eastern Uttar Pradesh (UP), India

R. N. Singh, N. D. University Agriculture and Technology, P.O. Dabha Semar, District Faizabad 224133, UP, India

BS caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan [*Cochliobolus miyabeanus* (Ito & Kuribayashi) Drechsler ex Dastur] and NBLs caused by *Cercospora oryzae* Miyake [*Sphaerulina oryzae* Hara] commonly occur in wet season (1 Jun-30 Nov) rice. We surveyed BS and NBLs in 5,000 sites in eastern UP, 1977-87. We also conducted 5 trials on their epidemiology and control.

Early-maturing (EM) timely sown (TS) (sown before 20 Jun) varieties escape NBLs and, sometimes, BS too. But in BS, postflowering infections in highly susceptible varieties can reach a

disease score of 6 by the hard dough stage. Two sprays of mancozeb, at 2 kg/1,000 liters water per ha, controlled BS but did not significantly increase yield. Grain discoloration was reduced by more than 50%.

Late sown medium maturity (MM) and TS late maturity (LM) varieties suffer most from BS and give full phenotypic expression to their genetic susceptibility. Infection commonly starts at maximum tillering and is severe (score of 9) by flowering time. In highly fertilized (120 to 150 kg N/ha) fields, 10 to 20% tillers lose normal foliage. Under moderate fertility (100 kg N/ha), yield loss is 10 to 20% in unprotected plots. Two sprays of carbendazim (0.05%) control the disease economically.

In late sown MM and normal sown LM varieties, BS and NBLs cause simultaneous infections, scoring 8 and 9 together (see table). Foliage loss of 5-25% and yield loss of 10-30% are common. Two sprays of mancozeb

Rice lines with high (6 and above) infection scores for BS, NBLs, and mixed BS-NBLs. Faizabad, UP, India, 1980, 1981, and 1986 wet seasons.

Designation	Lines (no.) with disease score ^a		
	BS	NBLs	BS-NBLs
IET7302, RP1579-1585-20-28	6	6	
CR194-523, KD14-1-39	6	7	
IET nos. 8002, 8101, 8540, 8543, 8544, 8845, 8582, 8583, 8642, 9186, 9187, 9188, RP2071-18-1-1	6	8	
CR317-166, CN836-3-8	6	9	
IET5656, RPI796-78-2-1-1-1	8	6	
WGL 47969, RP1579-1615-30-21-36	8	8	
RP1579-28-54	9	9	
IET6658			6
IET nos. 4087, 4155, 5882, 5883, 6144, 6272, Jagannath			8
IET nos. 5882, 5890, 5897, 6212, 6271, 6314, Pankaj			9

^aBy Standard evaluation system for rice (1980).

control the disease economically.

For optimum expression of genetic resistance or susceptibility to BS under natural disease pressure, MM and EM

varieties are sown on or after 1 and 20 Jul, respectively. For NBLs, however, sowing is delayed another 15 to 20 d. EM varieties that escape NBLs when

raooneed face maximum disease pressure and score 0 to 9. LM varieties get sufficient disease pressure even under TS situations. □

Control of rice bacterial blight (BB) by nickel nitrate

A. Chandrasekaran and P. Vidhyasekaran, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

We screened several chemicals to control rice BB. Rice variety IR20 was grown in the field Sep-Dec 1987. Chemicals at 3 concentrations were sprayed at the boot leaf stage, with 3 replications of 10 plants each for each treatment. The top 3 leaves were clip inoculated 24 h after spraying with a virulent isolate of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* at 10^8 colony-forming units/ml. Disease intensity was scored on 25 randomly selected leaves 20 d after inoculation and % leaf area affected was calculated (see table).

Nickel nitrate at 10^{-2} M effectively controlled the disease. No other chemical was effective. Nickel nitrate at 10^{-2} M to control BB was verified in 2 more independent tests in the greenhouse. □

Effect of different chemicals in inducing resistance to rice BB. Aduthurai, India, 1987.

Chemical	Concentration	Disease intensity	
		Grade value	Leaf area affected (%)
Nickel nitrate	10^{-2} M	1.8	3
	10^{-3} M	5.8	35
	10^{-4} M	6.5	44
Sodium fluoride	10^{-2} M	5.7	34
	10^{-3} M	7.4	60
	10^{-4} M	7.3	58
Calcium sulfate	0.2%	7.2	55
	0.5%	6.8	48
	1.0%	6.0	38
Magnesium sulfate	0.2%	5.8	35
	0.5%	6.8	48
	1.0%	6.2	40
Copper sulfate	0.2%	5.9	36
	0.5%	5.3	29
	1.0%	6.2	40
Ferrous sulfate	0.2%	5.9	36
	0.5%	6.8	48
	1.0%	6.3	41
Zinc sulfate	0.2%	6.3	41
	0.5%	7.0	50
	1.0%	7.7	68
Ammonium molybdate	10 ppm	6.3	41
	50 ppm	6.9	49
	100 ppm	7.0	50
Control		7.5	62
LSD (P=0.05)		1.3	2

Insect management

Brown planthopper (BPH) outbreak in Kanchana Buri Province, Thailand

C. Sindhusake, P. Vungsilabutr, and V. Yaklai, Rice Entomology Research Group, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkokhen, Bangkok 10900, Thailand

BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) has been a major insect pest of rice in the Central Plain of Thailand since 1973 dry season (DS), but there was no record of serious outbreaks in Yanchana Buri. In April 1988 DS under high temperatures (av

> 35 °C) at Kaosamsibhap Village, Tamaka District, BPH infestation occurred on about 240 ha with continuous irrigation and water standing in the fields.

It caused typical hopperburn symptoms on about 12.8 ha of rice variety RD7 (C4-63/GR88/ / Sigadis). The remaining area, planted to resistant variety RD23 (RD7/IR32//RDI), was not affected.

Double the recommended N (160 kg/ ha) had been applied as topdressing fertilizer at 40 d after sowing (DAS). Farmers sprayed monocrotophos 2-3 times to control rice thrips, leafhopper, and stem borers.

It is likely that these insecticide applications also caused the BPH outbreak. BPH populations sampled in

untreated fields exceeded 100 hoppers/ hill 83 DAS. Those populations probably came from fields with BPH resurgence. Populations of natural enemies of BPH (mirid bug and wolf spider) also were abundant. □

Chemical control of thrips and gall midge (GM) in rainfed lowland rice

S. K. Panda and N. Shi, Regional Research Station, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Chiplima, Sambabur, Orissa, India

We evaluated insecticides against GM *Orseolia oryzae* during 1988 wet season